

ANALYSIS OF OUT-OF-PLANE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITIES OF THREE-Dimensionally Woven Fabric Composites

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Abstract

This study investigates the effect of three-dimensional fiber reinforcement on the out-of-plane thermal conductivity of composite materials. Composite preforms with different fibers in thickness direction were fabricated. After infusion, using a Vacuum-Assisted Resin Transfer Molding process, their through thickness thermal conductivities were evaluated. The measured out-of-plane thermal conductivities showed significant increase compared to a typical laminated composite. Although the through thickness thermal conductivity of the samples increased with through thickness fiber volume fraction, the values did not match those predicted by a simple rule of mixture. Using Finite Element models to better understand the behavior of the composite material, improvements to an existing analytical model were performed to predict the effective thermal conductivity as a function of the composite material properties and in-contact thermal material properties.

Introduction

Fiber based composites offer the unique ability to tailor material properties locally. Localized matrix or fiber architecture changes can meet local mechanical, electrical, or thermal loads within a component or vehicle, without weight penalty or resort to additional external structures. However, traditional laminated uniaxial or biaxial composites have low through thickness thermal conductivities, which limit their use in a variety of aerospace applications. Leading edges in supersonic aircraft wings, inlet or exhaust areas of gas turbine engines, light weight heat exchangers, electronics packaging materials, doublers in satellite structures, and electromagnetic interference (EMI) enclosures all are subject to localized thermal loads which must be transferred through part thickness to adjacent cooler areas for subsequent radiation/convection, in part to mitigate internal stresses induced by reducing the thermal gradient across the part thickness. One common approach to increasing the through thickness conductivity of a composite, namely loading the resin with thermally conductive particles, can increase the conductivity only insignificantly. Also the use of expensive carbon nanotubes can increase the very low matrix thermal conductivity only by a factor of 10 [1]. One alternative

approach of achieving significant increase in the through-thickness thermal conductivity is to manufacture composites based on 3-D woven fiber architectures where the through-thickness fibers have high thermal conductivities. One commercially available fabric of this kind is 3WEAVE™ from 3TEX.

Description of 3 WEAVE™

The 3WEAVE™ process was originally developed at the NC State University College of Textiles and further refined and enhanced at 3TEX [2]. This process places several layers of fill (y-directional) and warp (x-directional) yarns in x-y plane without any crimp (contrary to conventional 2-D weaving process), thus providing straight bi-directional in-plane reinforcement (Figure 1). The multiple layers of warp and fill yarns are interlaced by a set of “z”-yarns, which holds the fabric together. The z-yarns provide a desirable level of out-of-plane strength, so the layers of warp and fill yarns cannot separate. The amount of “z”-fibers can be varied from less than 1% to more than 30% of the total fiber amount in the preform.

2-D weave formation

3-D (3WEAVE™) weave formation

Figure 1: Schematic of the 2-D and 3-D weaving processes

Using 3WEAVE™ process, fabrics have been produced with thickness up to 2 inches (5 cm), and widths up to 72 inches (183 cm). 3WEAVE™ process is “gentle” on the warp- and fill-directional fibers, thus improving the ability to use of rather brittle fibers, such as highly thermally conductive pitch yarns over traditional 2-D. Further, it is possible to fabricate directly some complex shapes of integral 3-D woven preforms. Importantly, different fiber kinds can be hybridized in a 3-D woven integral preform. Selective placement of fiber types through the preform can make a composite material with gradually changing properties. This could be used for tailoring density, stiffness, strength, thermal expansion, thermal conductivity, and other properties.

Thermal Conductivity Measurements

Thermal conductivity measurements were performed with a measuring cell built in-house at the Center for Composite Materials at the University of Delaware

according to ASTM E 1225 – 04 allowing measurements of circular samples with a diameter of 2” (50.8 mm) [3, 4]. Sample thicknesses can vary from 2 until 50 mm. The cell was placed on a cool plate to provide a heat sink with a constant temperature T_{sink} beneath the bottom plate. Temperature information read by thermistors were evaluated by a LabView-based program. Conductivity paste (OT-201 from Omega with $K = 2.3 \text{ W/(m K)}$) was used in order to facilitate coupling and to reduce interfacial thermal resistance. Prior to measurements, the thermal resistance R_{int} at the interfaces from meter bars and sample had to be determined using a stainless steel reference samples. R_{int} was determined to $533 \text{ (K mm}^2\text{)/W}$. The heat flux introduced by the cartridge heater was about 2000 W/m^2 . Calibration measurements were performed on isotropic specimens to determine the accuracy of the measuring cell. In addition, eleven composite samples made of 3WEAVETM by resin infusion in a VARTM-process were tested (Table 1). The thermal conductivities K of these samples were calculated according to a simple rule of mixtures [5]. It turned out that results for isotropic materials match their reference values well. However, the measured values for the composite samples with z-fiber reinforcement differed drastically from theoretically derived thermal conductivities despite the standard deviation for all material tests was less than $\pm 5 \%$.

TABLE 1: THERMAL AND CONDUCTIVITY PROPERTIES OF SAMPLE CONSTITUENTS USED

	base material	axial thermal conductivity K_a [W/(m K)]	radial thermal conductivity K_r [W/(m K)]
Cu-fiber	Copper	390	390
E-glass-fiber	glass	1.04	1.04
CN80-fiber	pitch	320	11
YS80-fiber	pitch	320	11
T300-fiber	PAN	100	11
T700-fiber	PAN	100	11
SC-15	epoxy	0.19	0.19

This leads to the conclusion that a simple model consisting of a parallel connection between out-of-plane conductivities of in-plane fibers and z-fibers can not be applied for these materials without alteration.

FE-Analysis

To get a better understanding of this result, the heat flow through a composite unit cell encompassing a single copper fiber sandwiched between two meter bars was

modeled by finite elements with a strictly vertical heat flux of $q'' = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$ and $T_{\text{sink}} = 20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Using this volume FE model with triangled meshes, variations in the v_{fz} of the copper fibers in the composite can be coupled with variations in the thermal conductivity of the meter bar. The copper volume fraction of the composite was varied between 0 and 100% and the thermal conductivity of the meter bar was also varied in steps between 0.1 and 1000 $\text{W}/(\text{m K})$. Thus, the effect of volume fraction and thermal conductivity on the measurement of thermal conductivity could be determined (Fig. 2). It is obvious that the measured conductivity is influenced not only by the volume fraction but also by the connecting meter bar material. The simple approach in terms of rule of mixture used above to estimate composite thermal conductivity seems to be the limit for connecting material conductivities approaching infinity. Higher thermal conductivity in the meter bar material increases the proportion of the heat flux through the copper fiber.

Figure 2: Thermal conductivity based on Cu-fiber volume fraction and meter bar material's thermal conductivity

In contrast, the low conductivity bar material allows little heterogenization of the heat flow, so the still homogeneous heat flux passes primarily through the area of the composite between z-fibers. As the thermal conductivity of the meter bar increases, significant heat flow passes through a larger meter bar area near the copper, as seen in the increasing size of the “mushroom” cap near the copper (Figure 3). Therefore, it has to be stated that the thermal conductivity of anisotropic or orthotropic material such as composites is no material but a system property because its heat flux influenced by adjoining materials. In addition, FEM-modeling was performed with the same scenario as described previously but only for a copper content of 10 %. However, this content was distributed in one, four, eight, sixteen, and thirty two fibers (so called entry ports) for samples with different thicknesses (1 mm, 2 mm, 4 mm, 8 mm, 16 mm, 32 mm). The result of this computation is depicted in Fig. 4.

Figure 3: FEM-Results of heat flux depending on meter bar conductivity

It is obvious that the distribution density of the sample also effects the thermal conductivity measurement. Furthermore, it turned out that contrary to isotropic materials also the thickness has an influence on the thermal conductivity (Fig. 4). This can be explained by an increasing effect of radial heat flow with depth.

Figure 4: Effect of thickness and number of entry ports

Improvements to Analytic Model

As described above, two effects unique to heterogeneous materials could be identified:

- Thermal conductivity of the material where the heterogenization takes place
- Distribution density of z-fibers

As common in describing properties of composites these effects can be taken into account by introducing factors to the simple rule of mixture, which can be calculated based on geometrical and material properties.

$$K_{3weave} = K_{z-fiber} \delta_{z-fiber} \eta_{KMat} \eta_{TD} + (1 - \delta_{z-fiber}) K_{in-planex,y} \quad (1)$$

In this equation, $\delta_{z-fiber}$ is the fiber volume fraction of z-fiber, η_{KMat} reflects the influence of the thermal conductivity of the adjoining material and η_{TD} takes the effect of the fiber distribution density and the thickness of the material into account. $K_{z-fiber}$ and $K_{in-planex,y}$ can be calculated according to [5].

$$\eta_{TD} = \tanh\left(\frac{\sqrt{\delta_{z-fiber}} t_{sample}}{2 d_{roving}}\right) \quad (2)$$

with t_{sample} as the sample thickness and d_{roving} the diameter of the roving. The dependency of η_{KMat} on the meter bar material can also be derived from the FE-results (Fig.1). The course of the graph can be described by a vertical shifted hyperbolic tangent function. Its course is also depicted in Fig. 5:

Figure 5: Dependency of η_{KMat} on meter bar material

$$\eta_{K_{Mat}} = \frac{1}{2} [\tanh(\log(0.1 K_{Mat})) + 1] \quad (3)$$

Eqn. 3 approximates empirically the effect of increase in diameter of the mushroom cap shaped heat flux area with the thermal conductivity of the meter bar material. $\eta_{K_{Mat}}$ becomes e.g. 0.6 for stainless steel as a meter bar material. This approach has to be done empirically due to the two-dimensional nature of the heat flux, because such problems can only be solved for special cases. The results of the improved model are shown in Fig. 6 in comparison to the simple model results proving the accuracy of the model introduced.

Figure 6: Comparison of simple rule of mixture values, new model and measured values

Discussion, Conclusions, and Perspectives

The thermal conductivity measurements on three-dimensionally reinforced composite samples described previously resulted in a drastic difference between expected and measured data. One explanation of these results involves the existence of discrete thermally high conductive heat flux entry ports in the composite samples under investigation. Thus, the thermal conductivity of a 3-D composite material has to be considered as a system property and not a material property due to the heat flux distribution capability of the materials connected. Furthermore, the distances between these ports define the ability of the composite system to homogenize the heat flux and can be expressed by the distance between fibers derived via fiber diameter. This ability is affected by the thermal conductivities of the adjoined

materials. Note that only isotropic neighboring materials were considered in this study. The development of a purely analytical thermal conduction model seems to very difficult if not impossible due to the two-dimensional nature of heat flux. However, the introduction of two factors to the simple rule mixture based on a parallel thermal connection model by taking into account fiber spacing and adjoining material led to reasonably accurate model predictions for the samples tested. In addition, this investigation showed that with a z-fiber volume content of about 6 % the maximum possible out-of-plane thermal conductivity can be increased by a factor of eight. This opens the possibility to design composite parts in terms of heat transfer having the thermal conductivity as design aspect to varied by fiber architecture and thus to seen equal to mechanical design criteria such as Young's modulus or strength.

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